

Trace analysis of uranium in coal fly ash by fluorimetry

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Abstract : Fluorimetry is one of the most suitable instrumental method for uranium analysis at trace level in different samples. A simple and fast fluorometric method has been developed for determination of trace level of uranium in fly ash obtained from Thermal Power Plant. The accurate determination of very low uranium content samples is carried out after the selective separation of uranium with ethyl acetate and aluminium nitrate. The known amount of non-aqueous extract fused with sodium carbonate-sodium fluoride flux at 800 °C temperature for 3 min in muffle furnace. Then fused mass is cooked and the fluorescence of the resultant bead is measured. The results showed that uranium present in the range of 0.00063 to 0.0032% of U₃O₈ in coal fly ash samples of different locations. The statistical data standard deviation is also calculated to observe reproducibility and reliability of results.

Introduction

The recovery of uranium from the earth crust and other resources has been gaining much attention in recent years because of its ever-increasing demand in nuclear technology. In India the primary resources of uranium are the main contributors to the industrial uranium production. The secondary resources such as rock phosphate, phosphoric acid, monazite, sea and river water, tailings of copper ore, coal fly ash etc. are also becoming important from the viewpoint of resource conservation¹. Amongst these secondary sources coal fly ash is also considered as an important unconventional source for uranium recovery in some other countries². The chemical composition of coal fly ash is depend on many factors e.g. coal quality, degree of pulverization, combustion technique and boiler operational conditions. It is well known that coal fly ash content a number of trace ele-

ments and radio-nuclides including uranium which are recognized as health hazards and having environmental impact^{3,4}.

The development of a method for analysis of uranium in coal fly ash is a challenging task because of matrix variation in samples of different locations. Due to the importance of uranium it is desirable to use an analytical technique that is highly sensitive, especially at trace level specific and even for a small sample.

The instrumental techniques are best suited for trace analysis of uranium in samples obtained from geological, environmental and biological origins. Various analytical procedures based on different instrumental techniques have been developed in the past for determination of uranium in samples of different origin⁵⁻⁷. Instrumental neutron activation analysis is applied to the determination of uranium and other 25 elements in coals and fly ash⁸. Differential pulse polarographic determination of uranium(VI) in complex materials after adsorption of its trifluoroethylxanthate cetyltrimethylammonium ion-associated complex on naphthalene adsorbent was developed by Puri *et al.*⁹. Kamata and his co-workers had done determination of trace amounts of thorium and uranium in coal ash by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry. It has been done after extraction with 2-thenoyltrifluoroacetone and back-extraction with dilute nitric acid¹⁰. The fluorimetry occupy a special position in the field of uranium analysis due to its ease of application, simplicity and cost factor of the instrument. The fluorimetry for determination of uranium in liquid samples is in use right from the days of Manhattan Project in USA. The fluorimetry is highly useful for uranium analysis in samples obtained from natural, biological, geological and environmental samples^{11,12}. A rapid laser fluorimetric method has been demonstrated for determination of uranium in coal fly ash and some other samples¹³. In nitric acid solutions uranium was determined by Fujimori *et al.*¹⁴. The laser induced fluorimetry has been used for in line uranium monitoring in reprocessing waste solution¹⁵. The fluorimetry has emerged a versatile analytical tool for uranium analysis in different types of samples^{16,17}.

The present paper deals with the application of fluorimetry for analysis of uranium in coal fly ash samples.

Experimental

Sample collection and preparation :

The coal fly ash samples were procured from Mineral Processing Divi-

sion, BARC, Hyderabad. These samples they had collected from different locations i.e. sample code with NTPC/RAM from Ramagundam (AP), SN/FA from Singareni Fly Ash (AP), SN/BA from Singareni Bottomash (AP), SLP Surat Lignite Power Plant (Gujarat) and NLP from Neyveli Lignite (Tamilnadu).

The collected coal fly ash samples were ground in Insmart make planetary Mill and powdered 100% passing 100 mesh then subjected for analysis.

Instrumentation :

The IR lamp was used for drying the non-aqueous extract in platinum dishes and Muffle furnace was used for fusing purpose. The fluorimetric measurements were made on an ECIL make Fluorimeter (Model FL-6224).

Chemical and reagents :

All the chemicals such as ethyl acetate, HF (48%), conc. HNO₃, aluminium nitrate, sodium carbonate and sodium fluoride used were of analytical reagent grade. The standard uranium solution (10 µg/ml) in nitric acid media was prepared by using U₃O₈, Uranium Chemical Standard, National Bureau of Standard, Washington 25 DC. All the solutions were made by using double distilled water.

Preparation of sample solution :

2 g of each coal fly ash sample was digested separately with 15 ml conc. HF till to dryness in platinum dish. Then 15 ml conc. HNO₃ added and again dried. The residue was dissolved in 10 ml conc. HNO₃ and transferred in a 100 ml beaker. About 50 ml distilled water added to this solution and boiled for 60 min the solution was cooled and the final vol. of solution was made up to 100 ml. After this the solution was filtered and subjected to extraction of uranium and quantitative determination.

Extraction and determination of uranium :

A 2 ml of aliquot of sample solution was taken in stoppered extraction tube and 5 ml of aluminium nitrate added. Then after adding 10 ml ethyl acetate the stoppered tube was shaken for 3 min and was allowed to settle for complete phase separation.

0.1 ml of the extract was pipette out into the fluorometric platinum dishes and the solvent was evaporated under IR lamp. Then 0.5 g of sodium

carbonate + sodium fluoride flux mixture was put into the dishes and was fused at 800 °C for 3 min. After cooling, the intensity of fluorescence of the fused beads was measured with ECIL make fluorometer. A set of standards and experimental blank were also run through the similar procedure and intensity of fluorescence measured was compared to know the unknown concentration of uranium in coal fly ash samples.

Results and discussion

The fluorimetry was used for determination of uranium in coal fly ash. The fluorometer was calibrated by making synthetic standard solution of different concentration using U_3O_8 standard before performing the analysis of coal fly ash samples. The fluorescent intensity was measured for each standard solution sample. It was observed that the fluorescent intensity is directly proportional to the concentration of U_3O_8 . The relation between fluorescent intensity and concentration of U_3O_8 is in Fig. 1. Then fluorescent intensity was measured for each coal fly ash sample. The results of analysis of uranium on above mentioned coal fly ash samples are summarised in Table 1, for each sample the mean of three tests along with standard deviation has been calculated. The standard deviation and shows the precision of determination and reliability of the observed data. It was also observed that chemical species like Fe, Mo, Cu, Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} do not interfere during analysis by said method. It is observed that in all coal fly ash samples,

Fig. 1. Relation between fluorescent intensity and concentration of U_3O_8 .

Table 1. Results of fluorometric analysis on coal fly ash samples

Sample code	U ₃ O ₈ (%)	Mean U ₃ O ₈ (%)	Standard deviation
NTPC/RAM/FA	0.0036 0.0032 0.0029	0.0032	0.00035
NTPC/RAM/Ash pond	0.0019 0.0021 0.0017	0.0019	0.00020
SN/BA	0.0013 0.0013 0.0009	0.0012	0.00023
SN/FA	0.0020 0.0024 0.0016	0.0020	0.00040
NLP/TS/II/B Ash	0.0006 0.0010 0.0010	0.00084	0.00020
NLP/TS/I/Clinker	0.0021 0.0017 0.0019	0.0019	0.00020
NLP/TS/I/BA	0.0012 0.0016 0.0020	0.0016	0.00040
NLP/TS/II/FA	0.0014 0.0017 0.0012	0.0014	0.00025
NLP/TS/I/FA	0.0017 0.0021 0.0013	0.0017	0.00040
SLP/FA ₁	0.0005 0.0008 0.0006	0.00063	0.00020
SLP/FA ₂	0.0015 0.0017 0.0013	0.0015	0.00020

U₃O₈ present at trace level and the concentration of U₃O₈ in different coal fly ash samples varied from 0.00063 to 0.0032% of U₃O₈.

The present analytical procedure based on fluorometric technique is a simple, convenient, fast and economic and it can be successfully employed for the quantitative determination of uranium in coal fly ash samples obtained from different locations.

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